

Family Life Education Programmes as Prerequisite for Curbing Drug Abuse Among Youths in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study examined family life education programmes as prerequisite for curbing drug abuse among youths in Rivers State. Four research objectives, four research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 5264 comprising 4341 members of community-based youth organisations and 923 local government health workers in Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 650 respondents comprising 362 members registered community based youth organisations used for the study and 288 health workers in the local government areas studied. Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size for the CBYO members. Multistage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample. Fifteen Local Government Areas were randomly selected. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled, "Family Life Education Programmes for Curbing Drug Abuse Among Youths Questionnaire". The face and content validity of the instrument was determined by the researcher's supervisor and two other experts from the Department of Adult Education and Community Development, Rivers State University. The reliability of the instrument was established through a test of internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha method with reliability coefficient (r) value of 0.84. The responses from the four research questions were analysed with Mean and Standard Deviation statistics, while the four null hypotheses were tested with t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that family life education programmes such as life skills training, intergenerational dialogue, family support, and reproductive health education programmes curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State to a high extent. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others, that Rivers State Primary Health Care Management Board should integrate age-appropriate reproductive health education into family life programmes which should be delivered by trained professionals, this initiative dispels myths and reduces adolescent anxiety, promoting healthy choices. By equipping youths with knowledge and confidence, it directly reduces their reliance on drugs as a maladaptive coping mechanism.

Keywords: Family Life Education, Programmes Drug Abuse, Youths

INTRODUCTION

Young people worldwide are crucial to societal development, bringing energy, creativity, and fresh perspectives to community and national growth. The concept of "youth" refers to a specific life stage, with definitions varying across legal, physiological, and chronological dimensions (Nsirim-Ovu, 2016). It is often characterised as the period between childhood and adulthood, marked by vitality and unique characteristics (Kobani & Taylor, 2017). For this study, "youth" refers to individuals aged 18-40, a vibrant demographic considered as the backbone of a nation's human resource. However, definitions of youth differ across societies as it is shaped by cultural, social, and economic factors. Furlong (2013) acknowledged the need to understand these variations when developing policies and programmes in addressing youth development and social issues like drug abuse. Undoubtedly, drug abuse among young people has become a pressing global public health issue, with far-reaching negative consequences for individuals, families, and societies. It involves the misuse of drugs, often without medical justification or in excessive doses. Martins (2011) defined drug abuse as the non-medical use of drugs, prohibited use, or excessive consumption, even of socially accepted substances like alcohol and cigarettes. This issue has spread across nations, communities, and institutions,

affecting young people's potential (Samuel & James, 2018). The 18-30 age group is particularly vulnerable, driven by curiosity, experimentation, and factors like peer pressure, low self-esteem, and family background (Nyaoke, 2013; Attah, Baba, & Audu, 2016). Undeniably, in Rivers State, the above identified factors has contributed to violent activities like cult-related killings, thuggery, and kidnapping. Therefore, addressing the issue of drug abuse is crucial to reducing violence among young people, requiring consideration of the underlying factors driving this behaviour.

In Rivers State, the abuse of drugs like cannabis, tramadol, and opioids among young people is a pressing concern with far-reaching consequences. Factors like peer pressure, curiosity, family issues, poverty, and mental health problems contribute to this trend (Jatau et al., 2021). The consequences are multifaceted, including physical and mental health issues, social problems, and economic burdens. Insecurity, cult clashes, and violent activities in Rivers State are often linked to youth drug abuse, affecting individuals, families, and communities. This unacceptable behaviour has long-term effects on young people's futures and well-being. According to Bulwark Intelligence (2015), violent activities in Rivers State are alarming, with families bearing emotional and financial burdens, and the state's economy suffering from

healthcare expenses, lost productivity, and crime-related costs. The Nigerian government has established the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) to combat drug abuse, focusing on law enforcement and prosecution. The agency, established in 1989, operates across the country, targeting drug trafficking and abuse. However, this approach has limitations, and a more holistic strategy is needed. Engaging youths in meaningful activities and promoting healthy lifestyles through family life education programmes can help address underlying issues driving drug abuse (Ibrahim, Eseadi, & Aguwa, 2021). Therefore, a shift from traditional security approaches to community-based initiatives, incorporating family life education, may be more effective in curbing drug abuse among youths in Rivers State.

Family life education is an educational process that equips individuals with knowledge, skills, and values to build strong, healthy relationships within families and communities, reducing social problems (National Council on Family Relations, 2018). It's a comprehensive approach of promoting healthy family relationships, resilience, and overall well-being (Brito & Cunningham, 2020). Family life education helps parents instill positive values and culture, crucial for peaceful coexistence. Oyebamiji and Otamiri (2016) highlighted its role in shaping children's attitudes and redirecting youth behaviour. Effective family life education programmes can include family life skills training, intergenerational dialogue, family support, and reproductive health education (Kumpfer & Alvarado, 2019). Undoubtedly, family life skills training programme is an intervention programme designed to equip family members with essential life skills, such as communication, problem-solving, and conflict resolution, to promote healthy family relationships and prevent substance abuse among youths. According to Haggerty, and Kosterman (2016), family life skills training programme can be effective in preventing substance abuse among youths by promoting positive family interactions and relationships. Similarly, Sandler, Wolchik, and Ayers (2022) acknowledged that family life skills training programme can help families develop the skills and strategies needed to navigate challenges and promote healthy development among youths.

On the other hand, intergenerational dialogue programmes are structured initiatives that bring together individuals from different age groups to foster understanding, collaboration, and knowledge sharing. These programmes aim to address pressing issues, such as social cohesion, peacebuilding, and sustainable development, by leveraging the collective wisdom and energy of diverse generations. According to Interpeace (2023), intergenerational dialogues have been

instrumental in promoting reconciliation and resilience in post-conflict settings, such as Rwanda and Somalia, by creating spaces for open storytelling and attentive listening. Similarly, Kumpfer and Alvarado (2019) emphasised the importance of family-based interventions, including intergenerational dialogues, in preventing substance abuse and promoting positive youth development. By facilitating intergenerational connections, these programmes can help bridge generational gaps, promote empathy, and empower communities to drive positive change in the behaviour of youths. .

Moreso, family support programme is designed to provide a support system for families, connecting them with resources, services, and community networks to promote healthy family relationships and prevent substance abuse. Dumas, and Graham (2020) acknowledged that family support network programme can be effective in preventing substance abuse among youths by providing families with access to resources, guidance, and support. On the other hand, Perrino, Brincks, Howe, and Prado (2022). emphasised that family support network programme can help families build resilience, cope with challenges, and promote positive relationships. Moreso, reproductive health education programme has been acknowledged to be highly effective in improving adolescents' knowledge and attitudes towards reproductive health. According to Agu et al. (2024), a structured sexual and reproductive health education intervention significantly improved knowledge of SRH among in-school adolescents in Southeast Nigeria. Similarly, Mbizvo et al. (2023) found that comprehensive sexuality education linked to sexual and reproductive health services reduced early and unintended pregnancies among in-school adolescent girls in Zambia. These studies acknowledged the importance of incorporating reproductive health education into school curricula to promote healthy behaviours and decision-making among young people

It is believed that proper implementation of family life education programmes by government agencies, NGOs, and other stakeholders can significantly curb youth involvement in drug abuse, thereby fostering peaceful and progressive communities. It is against this background that this study was designed to examine family life education programmes as prerequisite for curbing drug abuse among youths in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Youth drug abuse is a pressing issue in Rivers State, Nigeria, with severe consequences for individuals, families, and communities. Factors like poor family relationships, lack of guidance, and inadequate life skills contribute to this problem, leading to increased cult clashes, violence, and other crimes. While the

government has implemented measures like the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency's (NDLEA) War Against Drug Abuse (WADA) programme, these efforts have had limited success. A more effective approach may be to implement family life education programmes, such as family life skills training, intergenerational dialogue, family support, and reproductive health education, which can equip youths with necessary skills and knowledge to make positive life choices. However, the question remains: can these programmes effectively discourage drug abuse among youths in Rivers State? To answer this question therefore, was the problem of this study. To fill the gap in knowledge.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine family life education programmes as prerequisite for curbing drug abuse among youths in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. assess the extent to which family life skills training programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State, Nigeria
2. determine the extent to which intergenerational dialogue programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State, Nigeria.
3. find out the extent to which family support programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State, Nigeria.
4. Examine the extent to which reproductive health education programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. To what extent does family life skills training programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does intergenerational dialogue programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State, Nigeria?
3. To what extent does family support programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State, Nigeria?
4. To what extent does reproductive health education programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State, Nigeria.?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested for the study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health

extension workers on the extent that family life skills training programmes curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State

2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that intergenerational dialogue programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that family support programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State
4. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that reproductive health education programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted to examine family life education programmes as prerequisite for curbing drug abuse among youths in Rivers State. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 5,264 which included both 4341 members of registered community-based youth organisations and 923 local government health workers in the 23 Local Government Areas of Rivers State. (Source: Rivers State Ministry of Youth Development and Local Government departments of Health records, 2025). The sample size for the study was 650 respondents comprising 362 members of community-based youth organisations and 288 local government health workers in the study area. The Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size of the members of community-based youths organisations, as stipulated in appendix E. While the entire local government health workers in charge of health education in the selected local government areas were adopted for the study because it was a manageable size. However, multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample size of the study. The instrument for data collection was a structured closed-ended questionnaire titled "Family Life Education Programmes as Prerequisite for curbing Drug Abuse among Youths" The questionnaire was structured on four (4)-point rating scale of Very High Extent-VHE (4), High Extent-HE (3), Low Extent-LE (2), Very Low Extent- VLE. (1). The reliability of the instrument was done for each cluster of items in the questionnaire through a pilot study of 30 members of community-based youth organisation and

health education facilitators in Akwa Ibom State, outside the study population. The instrument was administered once to the group through the use of split-half method. The data collected were analysed using Cronbach Alpha Statistic method to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. Since the reliability was done for each cluster of items in the instrument, thus, a composite reliability coefficient of 0.82 was established and this indicated that the reliability index for all clusters of the instrument were greater than 0.50 which was high enough to ascertain that the instrument was reliable. Out of the total of 650 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 628 (96.69) copies were successfully retrieved, representing a high overall response rate of 96.69%. However, only 623 (97.90) copies of the questionnaire distributed were correctly filled which include 342 (98.60) from members of the community-based youth organisations, and the entire retrieved 281 (100.0) copies

from the local government health workers yielding a completion accuracy rate of 97.90%. The data collected from the research questions were analysed using mean and standard deviation statistics. Since the items were rated on four (4) point rating scale. Thus, the decision on each of the items were guided by the following rules; 1-1.49 =Very Low Extent, 1.5-2.49= Low Extent, 2.5-3.49 = High Extent, 3.5-4.00= Very High Extent. The null hypotheses were tested with the use of t-test statistic method at 0.05 level of significance and were accepted because the p-values were high than 0.05 significant level and would have been rejected if otherwise.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent does family life skills training programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State?

Table 1.: Mean Rating of Members of Community-Based Youth Organisations and Local Government Health Extension Workers on Extent to which Family Life Skills Training Programme Curb Drug Abuse Among Youths in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	(N = 1250)					
		Members of CBYOs (342)			LGA, Health workers (281)		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
1	Family life skills training programme help youths develop effective communication skills to resist drug abuse.	2.63	0.58	HE	2.61	0.54	HE
2	Family life skills training programme enhance youths' decision-making skills, reducing the likelihood of drug abuse.	2.67	0.59	HE	2.59	0.62	HE
3	Family life skills training programme promote healthy relationships between youths and their families, reducing the risk of drug abuse.	2.72	0.55	HE	2.57	0.61	HE
4	Family life skills training programme provide youths with coping mechanisms for stress and challenges without resorting to drug abuse.	2.75	0.63	HE	2.66	0.58	HE
5	Family life skills training programme help youths develop self-esteem and confidence, reducing their vulnerability to drug abuse.	2.86	0.72	HE	2.60	0.53	HE
6	Family life skills training programme can reduce the influence of peer pressure on youths to engage in drug abuse.	2.61	0.52	HE	2.84	0.89	HE
7	Family life skills training programme provide youths with problem-solving skills to manage challenges without resorting to drug abuse.	2.83	0.64	HE	2.72	0.75	HE
8	Family life skills training programme promote positive lifestyle choices among youths, reducing the risk of drug abuse.	2.84	0.73	HE	2.82	0.69	HE
9	Family life skills training programme can help youths develop goal-setting skills and plan for their future.	2.56	0.52	HE	2.56	0.61	HE
10	Family life skills training programme enhance youths' ability to manage emotions and behaviors, reducing the risk of drug abuse.	2.66	0.57	HE	2.67	0.79	HE
	Grand Mean	2.71	0.61	HE	2.65	0.66	HE

Source: Researcher’s Field Result, 2025.

Table 1 above for research question one, shows the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that family life skills training programme reduce drug abuse among youths Rivers State. Item 1 had mean scores of 2.63 and 2.61, with a standard deviation of 0.58 and 0.54. Item 2 had mean scores of 2.67 and 2.59, with standard deviation of 0.59 and 0.62. Item 33 had mean scores of 2.72 and 2.57, with a standard deviation of 0.55 and 0.61. Item 4 recorded mean scores of 2.75 and 2.66 with standard deviation of

0.63 and 0.58. Item 5 had mean scores of 2.86 and 2.60, with standard deviations of 0.72 and 0.53. Item 6, recorded a mean score of 2.61 and 2.84, with standard deviation of 0.52 and 0.89. Item 37 had a mean score of 2.83 and 2.72, with a standard deviation of 0.64 and 0.75. Item 8, recorded mean scores of 2.84 and 2.82, with standard deviation of 0.73 and 0.69. Item 39 had mean scores of 2.65 and 2.56 with standard deviations of 0.52 and 0.61, while Item 10 had mean scores of 2.66 and 2.67 with the standard deviations of 0.57 and 0.79 respectively. The grand mean of 2.71 and 2.66 for both

groups of respondents was recorded. The result revealed that members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers agreed that family life skills training programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State to a high extent.

Research Question 2: To what extent does intergenerational dialogue programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Rating of Members of Community-Based Youth Organisations and Local Government Health Extension Workers on Extent Intergenerational Dialogue Programme Curb Drug Abuse Among Youths in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	(N = 1250)					
		Members of CBYOs (342)			LGA, Health workers (281)		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
11	Family intergenerational dialogue programme increase awareness about the dangers of drug abuse.	3.22	0.78	HE	2.61	0.57	HE
12	intergenerational discussions in families help youths to make informed decisions about substance use	2.95	0.82	HE	2.69	0.52	HE
13	Sharing life experiences across generations in families discourages youths from engaging in drug abuse.	2.62	0.58	HE	2.75	0.65	HE
14	Family intergenerational dialogue programme promote healthy relationships to discourages drug abuse among youths	2.63	0.63	HE	2.67	0.51	HE
15	Family intergenerational dialogue programme foster sense of responsibilities that discourages abuse of drugs among youths	2.58	0.61	HE	2.70	0.68	HE
16	Family intergenerational communication help youths with moral courage to resist peer pressure related to drug abuse	2.51	0.54	HE	2.84	0.86	HE
17	Family intergenerational dialogue programme enable youths to cultivate good virtuous experience that discourages drug abuse	2.64	0.53	HE	2.57	0.55	HE
18	Family intergenerational dialogue programme enable youths to learn good behaviours from old generations	2.84	0.78	HE	2.76	0.67	HE
19	Family intergenerational dialogue programme promote positive role modeling and reduce drug abuse among youths	2.67	0.56	HE	2.80	0.68	HE
20	Intergenerational family dialogue programme strengthens family bonds and reduce the likelihood of drug abuse among youths	2.85	0.69	HE	2.67	0.59	HE
	Grand Mean	2.75	0.65	HE	2.71	0.63	HE

Source: Researcher’s Field Result, 2025.

Table 2 above for research question two, shows the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that intergenerational dialogue programme reduce drug abuse among youths in Rivers State. Item 11 had mean scores of 3.22 and 2.61, with a standard deviation of 0.78 and 0.57. Item 42 had mean scores of 2,95 and 2.69, with standard deviation of 0.82 and 0.52. Item 43 had mean scores of 2.62 and 2.75, with a standard deviation of 0.58 and 0.65. Item 44 recorded mean scores of 2.63 and 2.67, with standard deviation of 0.63 and 0.51. Item 45 had mean scores of 2.58 and 2.70, with standard deviations of 0.61 and 0.68. Item 46, recorded a mean score of 2.51 and 2.84, with standard deviation of 0.54 and 0.86. Item 47 had a mean scores of 2.64 and 2.57, with a standard deviation of 0.53 and

0.55. Item 48, recorded mean scores of 2.84 and 2.76, with standard deviation of 0.78 and 0.67. Item 49 had mean scores of 2.67 and 2.80 with standard deviations of 0.56 and 0.68, while Item 50 had mean scores of 2.85 and 2.67 with the standard deviations of 0.69 and 0.59 respectively. The grand mean of 2.75 and 2.71 for both groups of respondents was recorded. The result revealed that members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers agreed that intergenerational dialogue programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State to a high extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent does family support programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State ?

Table 3: Mean Rating of Members of Community-Based Youth Organisations and Local Government Health Extension Workers on Extent Family Support Programme Curb Drug Abuse Among Youths in Rivers State

S/N	Items	(N = 1250)					
		Members of CBYOs (342)			LGA, Health Workers (281)		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
51	Family support network programme provide emotional support to youths, reducing their vulnerability to drug abuse.	2.69	0.62	HE	2.61	0.59	HE
52	Family support network programme help youths develop resilience and coping skills to manage challenges without resorting to drug abuse.	2.67	0.59	HE	2.69	0.58	HE
53	Family support network programme promote positive relationships between youths and their family members, reducing the risk of drug abuse.	2.68	0.56	HE	2.64	0.56	HE
54	Family support network programme provide youths with access to resources and services that help prevent drug abuse.	2.65	0.58	HE	2.74	0.72	HE
55	Family support network programme can reduce the stigma associated with seeking help for drug abuse issues.	2.78	0.83	HE	2.66	0.61	HE
56	Family support programme help families develop effective communication skills, reducing the risk of drug abuse among youths.	2.72	0.65	HE	2.84	0.74	HE
57	Family support programme promote family involvement in drug abuse prevention efforts.	2.65	0.58	HE	2.72	0.79	HE
58	Family support programme provide families with strategies to manage stress and challenges, reducing the risk of drug abuse among youths.	2.54	0.53	HE	2.52	0.55	HE
59	9. Family support programme can help youths develop a sense of belonging and identity, reducing their vulnerability to drug abuse.	2.76	0.64	HE	2.86	0.68	HE
60	10. Family support programme enhance families' ability to provide a supportive environment that discourages drug abuse.	2.82	0.67	HE	2.76	0.79	HE
	Grand Mean	2.70	0.63	HE	2.70	0.66	HE

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2025.

Table 3 above for research question three shows the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that family support programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State. Item 51 had mean scores of 2.69 and 2.61, with a standard deviation of 0.62 and 0.59. Item 52 had mean scores of 2.67 and 2.69, with standard deviation of 0.59 and 0.58. Item 53 had mean scores of 2.68 and 2.64, with a standard deviation of 0.57 and 0.56. Item 54 recorded mean scores of 2.65 and 2.74, with standard deviation of 0.58 and 0.72. Item 55 had mean scores of 2.78 and 2.66, with standard deviations of 0.83 and 0.61. Item 56, recorded a mean score of 2.72 and 2.84, with standard deviation of 0.65 and 0.74. Item 57 had a mean scores of

2.65 and 2.72, with a standard deviation of 0.58 and 0.79. Item 58, recorded mean scores of 2.54 and 2.52, with standard deviation of 0.53 and 0.55. Item 59 had mean scores of 2.76 and 2.86 with standard deviations of 0.64 and 0.68 while Item 60 had mean scores of 2.82 and 2.76 with the standard deviations of 0.67 and 0.79 respectively. The grand mean of 2.70 and 2.70 for both groups of respondents was recorded. The result revealed that members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers shared strong opinion that family support programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State to a high extent.

Research Question 4: To what extent does reproductive health education programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State ?

Table 4: Mean Rating of Members of Community-Based Youth Organisations and Local Government Health Extension Workers on Extent Reproductive Health Education Programme Curb Drug Abuse Among Youths in Rivers State

		(N = 1250)						
S/N	Items	Members of CBYOs (342)			LGA, Health workers (281)			
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	
61	Reproductive health education in families fosters a positive attitude towards avoiding drug abuse among youths	2.86	0.88	HE	2.81	0.79	HE	
62	Family reproductive health education increases awareness among youths about the risk of drug abuse	2.57	0.69	HE	2.69	0.59	HE	
63	Reproductive health education in families help youths make informed decision about substance abuse	2.82	0.91	HE	2.56	0.58	HE	
64	Family discussion about reproductive health reduce the likelihood of drug experience	2.75	0.68	HE	2.66	0.55	HE	
65	Family life education promotes healthy lifestyle choices among youths	2.58	0.59	HE	2.60	0.52	HE	
66	Family reproductive health education is effective in preventing drug abuse among youths	2.61	0.62	HE	2.74	0.62	HE	
67	Understanding the link between reproductive health and drug abuse discourages substance use	2.59	0.56	HE	2.55	0.57	HE	
68	Family based reproductive health education reduces the risk of drug abuse among youths	2.64	0.63	HE	2.57	0.69	HE	
69	Family reproductive health education improves self -esteem among youths thereby reducing their likelihood of involving in drug related activities.	2.68	0.66	HE	2.62	0.58	HE	
70	Family reproductive health education promote overall wellbeing thereby decreasing youth engagement in risky behaviour associated with substance abuse	2.70	0.67	HE	2.65	0.64	HE	
	Grand Mean	2.68	0.69	HE	2.65	0.61	HE	

Source: Researcher’s Field Result, 2025.

Table 4 above for research question four, shows the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that reproductive health education programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State. Item 61 had mean scores of 2.86 and 2.81, with a standard deviation of 0.88 and 0.79. Item 62 had mean scores of 2.57 and 2.69, with standard deviation of 0.69 and 0.59. Item 63 had mean scores of 2.82 and 2.56, with a standard deviation of 0.91 and 0.58. Item 64 recorded mean scores of 2.75 and 2.66, with standard deviation of 0.68 and 0.55. Item 65 had mean scores of 2.58 and 2.60, with standard deviations of 0.59 and 0.52. Item 66, recorded a mean score of 2.61 and 2.74, with standard deviation of 0.62 and 0.63. Item 67 had a mean score of 2.59 and 2.55, with a standard deviation of 0.56 and 0.57. Item 68, recorded mean scores of 2.64 and 2.57, with standard deviation of 0.63 and 0.69. Item 69 had mean scores of 2.68 and 2.62 with standard deviations

of 0.66 and 0.58 while Item 70 had mean scores of 2.70 and 2.65 with the standard deviations of 0.67 and 0.64 respectively. The grand mean of 2.68 and 2.65 for both groups of respondents was recorded. The result revealed that members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers agreed that reproductive health education programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State to a high extent.

Test of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that family life skills training programmes curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-test Analysis of Difference Between Members of Community Based Youth Organisations and Local Government Health Extension Workers on the Extent that Family Life Skills Training Programmes Curb Drug Abuse Among Youths in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	t- cal	p-value	Level of Sign.	Decision
Members,CBYOs,	342	2.71	0.61	621	1.61	0.58	0.05	Accepted
LGA, Health workers	28	2.66	0.66					

Table 5 above shows that p-value of 0.58 is greater than 0.05 level of significance at 621 degree of freedom indicating that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that family life skills training programmes curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers

State. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that intergenerational dialogue programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State

Table 6: t-test t-test Analysis of Difference Between Members of Community Based Youth Organisations and Local Government Health Extension Workers on the Extent that Intergenerational Dialogue Programme Curb Drug Abuse Among Youths in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	t-cal	P-value	Level of Sign.	Decision
Members CBYOs,	34	2.75	0.65	621	1.86	0.79	0.05	Accepted
LGA, Health workers	281	2.71	0.63					

Table 6 above shows that p-value of 0.79 is greater than 0.05 level of significance at 621 degree of freedom. This indicated that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that intergenerational dialogue programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers

State. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that family support programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State

Table 7: t-test Analysis of Difference Between Members of Community Based Youth Organisations and Local Government Health Extension Workers on the Extent that Family Support Programme Curb Drug Abuse Among Youths in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	p-value	s/level	Decision
Members,CBYOs,	342	2.70	0.63	621	0.96	0.54	0.05	Accepted
LGA, Health workers	281	2.70	0.66					

Table .7 above, shows that p-value of 0.54 is greater than 0.05 level of significance at 621 degree of freedom indicating that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that family support network programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent

that reproductive health education programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State.

Table .8: t-test Analysis of Difference Between Members of Community Based Youth Organisations and Local Government Health Extension Workers on the Extent that Reproductive Health Education Programme Curb Drug Abuse Among Youths in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t-cal	p-value	Level of Sign.	Decision
Members,CBYOs, embers	342	2.68	0.70	621	0.58	0.55	0.05	Accepted
LGA, Health workers	281	2.65	0.61					

Table 8 above, shows that p-value of 0.54 is greater than 0.05 level of significance at 621 degree of freedom indicating that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that reproductive health education programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The finding from the study in research question 1 with a grand mean of 2.71 and 2.66 revealed that both members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers agreed that family life skills training programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State to a high extent as evidenced in table 1 that family life skills training programme help youths develop effective communication skills to resist drug abuse, enhance youths' decision-making skills, reducing the likelihood of drug abuse, promote healthy relationships between youths and their families, reducing the risk of drug abuse, provide youths with coping mechanisms for stress and challenges without resorting to drug abuse, help youths develop self-esteem and confidence, reducing their vulnerability to drug abuse, reduce the influence of peer pressure on youths to engage in drug abuse, provide youths with problem-solving skills to manage challenges without resorting to drug abuse, promote positive lifestyle choices among youths, reducing the risk of drug abuse, help youths develop goal-setting skills and plan for their future, and enhance youths' ability to manage emotions and behaviors, reducing the risk of drug abuse. Corresponding hypothesis 1 affirmed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local

government health extension workers on the extent that family life skills training programme reduce drug abuse among youths in Rivers State. The finding in research question 1 is similar to the finding of Wight, (2016) that family life skills training programme builds core competencies within the family system that reduce vulnerability to drug abuse by systematically enhancing problem-solving, conflict resolution, and emotional regulation skills for both parents and youths. Similarly, Ogide and Brown (2022) also find that family life skills training programme improves the overall functionality of the family which reduces stress and maladaptive coping mechanisms and that these skills create a home environment that is inherently less conducive to the development of substance abuse behaviours

The finding from the study in research question 2 with a grand mean of 2.75 and 2.71 revealed that both members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers agreed that intergenerational dialogue programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State to a high extent as evidenced in table 2 that intergenerational dialogue programme increase awareness about the dangers of drug abuse, help youths to make informed decisions about substance use, discourages youths from engaging in drug abuse, promote healthy relationships to discourages drug abuse among youths, foster sense of responsibilities that discourages abuse of drugs among youths, help youths with moral courage to resist peer pressure related to drug abuse, enable youths to cultivate good virtuous experience that discourages drug abuse, enable youths to learn good behaviours from old generations, promote positive role modeling and reduce drug abuse among youths, and strengthens family bonds and reduce the likelihood of drug abuse among youths. Corresponding hypothesis 2 confirmed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of

community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that intergenerational dialogue programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State. The finding in research question 2 is related to the finding of Nwosu and Eke, (2023) that dialogue facilitate the transfer of experiential knowledge, wisdom, and cultural norms from elders to the younger generation, fostering a sense of identity and belonging that can buffer against negative external influences. Moreso, the finding corroborated with the finding of Uchendu and Okeke, (2021) that intergenerational dialogue does not only strengthens ethnic pride and self-esteem but also provides youths with positive role models and a broader, more supportive social network, which are critical protective factors.

The finding from Table 3 for research question 3 with a grand mean of 2.70 and 2.70 revealed that both members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers agreed that family support programme reduce drug abuse among youths in Rivers State to a high extent, hence Family support network programme provide emotional support to youths which reduces their vulnerability to drug abuse, help youths develop resilience and coping skills to manage challenges without resorting to drug abuse, promote positive relationships between youths and their family members, reducing the risk of drug abuse, provide youths with access to resources and services that help prevent drug abuse, reduce the stigma associated with seeking help for drug abuse issues, help families develop effective communication skills that reduces the risk of drug abuse among youths, promote family involvement in drug abuse prevention efforts, provide families with strategies to manage stress and challenges to reduce the risk of drug abuse among youths. help youths develop a sense of belonging and identity, reducing their vulnerability to drug abuse, enhance families' ability to provide a supportive environment that discourages drug abuse. Corresponding hypothesis 3 confirmed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that family support programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State. The finding in research question 3 agree with the finding of Gurung and Turner, (2018) that Programmes that bolster emotional and instrumental support within the family act as a powerful buffer against the stressors and traumas that often precipitate substance use. Similarly, Ibegbunam and Onyema, (2020) find that when youths perceive their family as a reliable source of unconditional support, it enhances their psychological well-being and reduces the likelihood of turning to drugs as a coping mechanism, thereby promoting healthier developmental pathways. The finding also align with the position of Dumas, Arriaga, and Begle (2020) that

family support networks play a critical role in reducing adolescent substance use among youths in families, and that parental involvement, family cohesion, and community engagement is very important in preventing substance use among adolescents.

The finding from the study in research question 4 with a grand mean of 2.68 and 2.65 revealed that both members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers agreed that reproductive health education programme reduce drug abuse among youths in Rivers State to a high extent as evidenced in table 4. that reproductive health education families fosters a positive attitude towards avoiding drug abuse among youths, increases awareness among youths about the risk of drug abuse, help youths make informed decision about substance abuse, reduce the likelihood of drug experience, promotes healthy lifestyle choices among youths, effective in preventing drug abuse among youths, discourages substance use, reduces the risk of drug abuse among youths, improves self -esteem among youths thereby reducing their likelihood of involving in drug related activities, and promote overall wellbeing thereby decreasing youth engagement in risky behaviour associated with substance abuse. Corresponding hypothesis 4 affirmed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community-based youth organisations and local government health extension workers on the extent that reproductive health education programme curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State.

Findings in research question 4 is in line with the finding of Akani and Nkwocha (2022) that reproductive health education programmes empower youths with crucial information that reduces risky behaviours, including the use of substances in social or sexual contexts. The finding also relate with the position of Peterson and John, (2016) that by fostering a sense of self-efficacy and bodily autonomy, comprehensive reproductive health education helps youths make more informed decisions overall, which translates into a reduced propensity to experiment with or regularly use illicit drugs.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that family life education programmes, including life skills training, intergenerational dialogue, family support, and reproductive health education, significantly curb drug abuse among youths in Rivers State to a high extent. These programmes address the complex issue of youth substance abuse by strengthening family relationships, building resilience, transmitting cultural values, and providing practical skills, thereby tackling the problem at individual and familial levels. The findings suggest that a comprehensive, integrated approach is necessary,

combining multiple strategies to create a robust protective framework, rather than relying on a single solution.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings of this study, the researcher made the following recommendations:

1. Non-governmental organisations should partner with community health extension workers to deliver practical skills workshops with both parents and youths as target audience, focusing on competencies such as conflict resolution, financial literacy, stress management, and effective communication which build the resilience of the family unit and provide constructive alternatives to the escapism often sought through substance use.
2. community-based youth organisations and elders' councils should regularly organise structured forums and social events designed to facilitate open conversation between youths and older community members focusing on creating a safe space for sharing perspectives, challenges, and experiences, thereby bridging the understanding gap and fostering mutual respect. This process allows for the organic transfer of wisdom and social norms that protect youths against drug abuse.
3. The Rivers State Ministry of Women Affairs should lead by expanding Family Support Units to offer community counselling and parent groups. This safety net assists families facing stress and economic hardship, mitigating key risk factors for youth drug abuse. Strengthening the family's coping capacity effectively reduces the likelihood of substance use.
4. Rivers State Primary Health Care Management Board should integrate age-appropriate reproductive health education into family life programmes which should be delivered by trained professionals, this initiative dispels myths and reduces adolescent anxiety, promoting healthy choices. By equipping youths with knowledge and confidence, it directly reduces their reliance on drugs as a maladaptive coping mechanism.

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